

Impact of environmental variables on selective vector-borne diseases in the state of West Bengal, India

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Abstract

Environmental variables play a crucial role in spreading several infectious diseases, particularly the vector-borne diseases, like, malaria and dengue. There are strong evidences on the regulatory role of environmental variables on the transmission and spreading of malaria and dengue across different parts of the world. Considering this background, the present research aims to evaluate the influences of atmospheric carbon dioxide, air temperature, relative humidity, and precipitation on two common vector-borne diseases, namely, malaria and dengue, based on the data bank of more than two decades (2001-2022). The work was carried out in two major districts of West Bengal (India), namely, Darjeeling and Canning located in the northern and southernmost parts of the state of West Bengal. Correlation carried out on the data sets showed significant positive influences of the environmental variables on both malaria and dengue in Canning, but the influences were not statistically significant in Darjeeling, which may be attributed to the topographical situations of the two sites.

Keywords: Environmental variables, malaria, dengue, West Bengal (India).

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1. Introduction

Vector borne diseases are increasing at a great pace throughout the World, and the maritime state of West Bengal in India is no exception to this normal trend. Malaria and dengue are the two common mosquito borne diseases in the region.

Malaria in India is primarily caused by the transmission of Plasmodium parasites through the bites of infected female Anopheles mosquitoes. There are four main species of Anopheles mosquitoes responsible for the transmission of malaria in India as listed here.

1. *Anopheles culicifacies*: This is the most common and widely distributed species, responsible for most malaria cases in rural areas.
2. *Anopheles stephensi*: This species is mainly found in urban and peri-urban areas and is a significant vector in cities.
3. *Anopheles fluviatilis*: Commonly found in hilly and forested regions of India, this mosquito species also contributes to malaria transmission.
4. *Anopheles dirus*: Predominantly found in the northeastern states of India, this species is known for its role in malaria transmission in forested and hilly areas.

Figure 1. Image of *Anopheles culicifacies* mosquito.

Source: Authors.

Figure 1 is the illustration of the *Anopheles culicifacies* mosquito, which is the most common vector for malaria in India.

Dengue fever in India is primarily caused by the dengue virus, which is transmitted to humans through the bites of infected female mosquitoes, specifically those of the Aedes species. The two main vectors for dengue transmission are:

1. *Aedes aegypti*: This mosquito is the primary vector for the transmission of the dengue virus. It prefers to breed in man-made containers like pots, drums, and other items that collect rainwater. *Aedes aegypti* is highly adapted to urban environments.
2. *Aedes albopictus*: Also known as the Asian tiger mosquito, this species is a secondary dengue vector. It is more commonly found in suburban and rural areas but has adapted to a variety of environments.

Figure 2 is the diagram of an *Aedes aegypti* mosquito, highlighting its distinctive black and white patterned body and legs.

Figure 2. Image of *Aedes aegypti* mosquito.

Source: Authors.

Environmental variables play a significant role in the transmission and prevalence of both malaria

and dengue fever. Their impacts on each of these vector-borne diseases are substantiated separately.

1.1 Malaria

Malaria transmission is highly sensitive to temperature. An increase in temperature can accelerate the development of the malaria parasite within mosquitoes, shorten the incubation period, and expand the geographical range of mosquito breeding habitats.

Rainfall patterns influence the availability of breeding sites for mosquitoes. Heavy rainfall can create stagnant water pools, which serve as breeding grounds for malaria-transmitting mosquitoes. However, excessive rainfall can also flush away larvae from breeding sites, reducing mosquito populations.

High humidity levels facilitate the survival of mosquitoes and the development of the malaria parasite within them. Optimal humidity levels provide favourable conditions for virus replication within mosquitoes, leading to higher viral loads and increased infectiousness. Humid environments provide suitable conditions for mosquito breeding and increase their longevity.

Climate change driven by elevated level of carbon dioxide can cause ecological disruptions that affect mosquito habitat suitability and disease transmission dynamics. Deforestation and habitat fragmentation resulting from climate change-related factors can create new ecological niches for mosquitoes and increase human-mosquito contact, thereby enhancing disease transmission risk. Warmer temperatures can accelerate the development and reproduction of mosquito vectors, such as Anopheles mosquitoes (malaria), thereby increasing their abundance and expanding their geographical range. This, in turn, can lead to more frequent and widespread transmission of malaria in regions where these diseases are endemic or emerging.

1.2 Dengue

Dengue transmission is significantly influenced by temperature. Warmer temperatures accelerate the replication of the dengue virus within mosquitoes, shorten the extrinsic incubation period, and increase the rate of viral transmission. Also, warmer temperatures may increase the activity and aggressiveness of mosquitoes, leading to more frequent biting and higher rates of disease transmission to humans.

Dengue transmission is closely linked to rainfall patterns. Heavy rainfall creates breeding sites for the Aedes mosquitoes, the vectors responsible for transmitting dengue virus. However, excessive rainfall can also flush away breeding sites and kill the mosquito larvae, disrupting mosquito populations temporarily.

Dengue fever is primarily an urban disease, as urban environments provide ample breeding sites for Aedes mosquitoes in the form of water containers, car tyres, and other discarded items that collect water. Rapid urbanization, especially in tropical regions, contributes to the proliferation of mosquito breeding sites and increases the risk of dengue outbreaks.

Environmental variables also interact with human behaviour, *e.g.*, increased rainfall may lead to the accumulation of water in containers around households, providing ideal breeding sites for mosquitoes. Additionally, temperature and humidity influence human behaviour, such as the use of air conditioning or sleeping outdoors, which can affect exposure to mosquito bites.

Elevated atmospheric carbon dioxide levels contribute to global climate change by trapping heat in the Earth's atmosphere, leading to higher temperatures. Warmer temperatures can accelerate the development and reproduction of mosquito vectors, such as Aedes mosquitoes (dengue), thereby increasing their abundance and expanding their geographical range. This, in turn, can lead to more frequent and widespread transmission of dengue in regions where these diseases are endemic or emerging.

Based on the above information, the present research was carried out to assess the influence of four most relevant environmental variables, namely near surface atmospheric carbon dioxide level, air temperature, relative humidity, and precipitation [1] on the total malaria and dengue incidences in two districts of the state of West Bengal with variable topography and weather conditions.

2. Methodology

In this phase, primary and secondary data were collected on relevant environmental variables related closely to climate change like near surface atmospheric carbon dioxide, rainfall, air temperature and humidity. Field visits were done in both the districts, namely, Darjeeling and Canning located in North and South Bengal

respectively. Data on environmental variables were mostly collected from India Meteorological Department (IMD), except the near surface atmospheric carbon dioxide levels that were carried out as per the standard protocol [2] Inter-relationships between the two sets of variables (dependent variables = cases of vector borne diseases and independent variables = environmental variables) were assessed through correlation coefficient values.

3. Results

Figures (3-6) represent the temporal variations of environmental variables in the selected study sites.

Figure 3: Near surface atmospheric carbon dioxide level (ppm) around the selected sites.

Source: Authors.

Figure 4: Air temperature (°C) in and around the selected sites.

Source: Authors.

Figure 5: Relative humidity (%) in and around the selected sites.

Source: Authors.

Figure 6: Precipitation (cm) around the selected sites

Source: Authors.

Figures 7 and 8 represent the temporal variations of the number of cases exposed to dengue and malaria respectively in and around the selected study sites.

Figure 7: Number of cases exposed to dengue in Canning and Darjeeling.

Source: Authors.

Figure 8: Number of cases exposed to malaria in Canning and Darjeeling.

Source: Authors.

4. Discussion

Malaria prevalence and epidemic resurgence has been significantly associated with temperature and rainfall, and to El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) events in many countries like South Africa, the East African highlands, and

Madagascar [3-5]. Like dengue, the role of epidemiological, socio-economic, and environmental factors in driving malaria transmission has been noted in many geographical areas [3]. Precipitation and/or temperature have been positively associated with malaria incidence

and vector population in Americas [[6], Europe [7], Iran [8], Pakistan [[9,10], China [11] and Nepal [12].

According to Watts et al., from 1950 to 2018, the global climate suitability for the transmission of dengue increased by almost 10% for *Aedes aegypti* and 15% for *A. albopictus*, the primary vectors of dengue virus [13]. Ongoing climate change is anticipated to further extend the latitudinal range *A. aegypti* mosquitoes, increasing the population at risk of dengue in several African countries in Southern and Central Africa [4]. Similar increases in climatically suitable areas for the establishment of *A. albopictus* are anticipated in western, central, and eastern Europe, including in southeast England, with increasing risk for dengue transmission around Mediterranean and Adriatic coasts towards the end of twenty-first century [7,14]. In China, there has been a trend of expanded geographical region for dengue infections, from South to North China in line with warming

temperatures [15] and expansion of the geographic range of *A. albopictus* [11].

In the present study regions, we observed two different patterns and striking variations between Canning and Darjeeling, both in terms of malaria and dengue cases. In Canning, which is in the southernmost part of the state of West Bengal, both vector-borne diseases exhibit a symmetry. However, in Darjeeling, which is a hilly zone in the northernmost part of the state, the diseases differ in terms of time-series analysis. Correlation carried out on data sets showed significant positive influences of the environmental variables on both malaria and dengue in Canning (Table 4), but the influences were not statistically significant in Darjeeling (Table 3) which maybe the impact of topographical situations of the two sites.

Table 3. Inter-relationship between environmental variables and vector borne diseases (malaria and dengue) at Darjeeling.

	CO ₂ (ppm)	Air temp (°C)	Relative humidity (%)	Precipitation (cm)	Total Malaria cases	Total Dengue cases
CO ₂ (ppm)	1	-	-	-	-	-
Air temp (°C)	0.8541	1	-	-	-	-
Relative humidity (%)	0.9710	0.9022	1	-	-	-
Precipitation (cm)	0.6511	0.9004	0.7219	1	-	-
Total Malaria cases	-0.1112	-0.2890	-0.1786	-0.3772	1	-
Total Dengue cases	0.2215	0.3770	0.2670	0.2107	-0.1856	1

Index:

p < 0.01	Insignificant correlation
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Source: Authors.

Table 4. Inter-relationship between environmental variables and vector borne diseases (malaria and dengue) at Canning

	CO ₂ (ppm)	Air temp (°C)	Relative humidity (%)	Precipitation (cm)	Total Malaria cases	Total Dengue cases
CO ₂ (ppm)	1	-	-	-	-	-
Air temp (°C)	0.9491	1	-	-	-	-
Relative humidity (%)	0.9217	0.9686	1	-	-	-
Precipitation (cm)	0.7314	0.8650	0.8390	1	-	-
Total Malaria cases	0.8373	0.8426	0.8520	0.6519	1	-
Total Dengue cases	0.5084	0.6644	0.5878	0.7943	0.3274	1

Index:

p < 0.01	Insignificant correlation
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Source: Authors.

5. Conclusions

The research focused on evaluating how environmental factors such as atmospheric carbon dioxide, air temperature, relative humidity, and precipitation influence the transmission of vector-borne diseases, specifically malaria and dengue.

Data and Duration: The study analyzed data spanning over two decades, from 2001 to 2022, to understand these relationships.

Geographic Focus: The investigation was carried out in two major districts of West Bengal, India — Darjeeling and Canning. These locations represent the northern and southern extremes of the state, providing a diverse range of environmental conditions.

Findings in Canning: In Canning, there was a significant positive correlation between the environmental variables studied and the incidence of malaria and dengue. This indicates that changes in these environmental factors are strongly associated with increased transmission of these diseases in this region.

Findings in Darjeeling: In contrast, Darjeeling did not show statistically significant correlations between the same environmental variables and disease incidence. This lack of significance could be attributed to the unique high altitude related

topographical features of Darjeeling, which may influence local climate and vector behaviour differently than in Canning.

Management strategies: The research highlights the importance of considering local environmental and topographical factors when assessing the risk and spread of vector-borne diseases like malaria and dengue. While some areas may show strong environmental influences, others might not, emphasizing the need for location-specific disease management and prevention strategies.

References

- [1] A. Mitra, "Sensitivity of mangrove ecosystem to changing climate". Springer, New Delhi, Heidelberg, New York, Dordrecht, London. ISBN-10: 8132215087; ISBN-13: 2013 978-8132215080. ISBN 978-81-322-1509-7 (eBook), XIX: pp. 323 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-81-322-1509-7>, 2013.
- [2] Suresh Kumar Agarwal, Fazli, pardis; Sufia Zaman and Abhijit Mitra. "Near surface Air temperature and carbon dioxide in Indian Sundarbans: A Time series Analysis." Parana Journal of Science and Education, 2018, 4 (1), 10-15, 2018.

- [3] GJ Abiodun, BO Adebisi, RO Abiodun, O Oladimeji, KE Oladimeji, AM Adeola, et al. "Investigating the resurgence of malaria prevalence in South Africa between 2015 and 2018: a scoping review." *Open Public Health J.* 2020;13(1):119–25, **2020**
- [4] C. Giesen, J. Roche, L. Redondo-Bravo, C. Ruiz-Huerta, D. Gomez-Barroso, A. Benito, et al. "The impact of climate change on mosquito-borne diseases in Africa. *Pathog Glob Health.*" 2020;114(6):287-301, **2020**.
- [5] MLH. Mabaso, NC. Ndlovu. "Critical review of research literature on climate-driven malaria epidemics in sub-Saharan Africa. *Public Health.*" 2012;126(11):909–19, **2012**.
- [6] MS. López, GV. Müller, WF. Sione. "Analysis of the spatial distribution of scientific publications regarding vector-borne diseases related to climate variability in South America." *Spat Epidemiol.* 2018; 26:35–93, **2018**.
- [7] S. Brugueras, B. Fernández-Martínez, J. Martínez-de la Puente, J. Figuerola, TM. Porro, C. Rius, et al. "Environmental drivers, climate change and emergent diseases transmitted by mosquitoes and their vectors in southern Europe: a systematic review." *Environ Res.* 2020;191:110038, **2020**.
- [8] J. Babaie, M. Barati, M. Azizi, A. Epthekhari, SJ. Sadat. "A systematic evidence review of the effect of climate change on malaria in Iran." *J Parasit Dis.* 2018;42(3):331–40, **2018**.
- [9] T Ahmed, M Scholz, F Al-Faraj, W Niaz. "Water-related impacts of climate change on agriculture and subsequently on public health: a review for generalists with particular reference to Pakistan." *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2016;13(11):1051, **2016**.
- [10] T Ahmed, MZ Hyder, I Liaqat, M Scholz. "Climatic conditions: conventional and nanotechnology-based methods for the control of mosquito vectors causing human health issues." *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2019;16(17):3165, **2019**.
- [11] L Bai, LC Morton, Q Liu. "Climate change and mosquito-borne diseases in China: a review. *Glob Health.*" 2013;9:10, **2013**.
- [12] M Dhimal, B Ahrens, U Kuch. "Climate change and spatiotemporal distributions of vector-borne diseases in Nepal - a systematic synthesis of literature." *PLoS One.* 2015;10(6):e0129869, **2015**.
- [13] N Watts, M Amann, N Arnell, S Ayeb-Karlsson, J Beagley, K Belesova, et al. "The 2020 report of The Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: responding to converging crises." *Lancet.* 2021;397(10269):129–70, **2021**.
- [14] JM Medlock, SA Leach. "Effect of climate change on vector-borne disease risk in the UK. *Lancet Infect Dis.*" 2015;15(6):721 –30, **2015**.
- [15] L Yi, X Xu, W Ge, H Xue, J Li, D Li, et al. "The impact of climate variability on infectious disease transmission in China: current knowledge and further directions." *Environ Res.* 2019; 173:255-261, **2019**.